

Enhancing Problem-Solving Competencies for Engineering Students Using Flipped Classroom: A Case Study in a College Physics Course in Vietnam

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 05, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Problem-Solving Competencies, Flipped Classroom, Competency-Based Learning, Instructional Design, College Physics Course.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7405316</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of flipped classroom using an instructional design on the physics competencies of engineering students. In this context, a mixed research method was used. In the quantitative session, a pre-test/post-test control group study was used using the problem-solving test. As for the qualitative session, the qualitative method was used using a semi-interview as a data collection instrument. In the experimental group, flipped learning using an instructional design was used, while in the control group the conventional method was applied. The first-year engineering students of the electrical and electronic engineering department at Cao Thang Technical College participated in the study. The independent sample t-test was used to test the mean scores on students' problem-solving competency in physics between the experimental and control groups. The thematic analysis method was conducted to analyze the interview data. The results demonstrated that there is a difference in the scores on students' problem-solving competency in physics between the experimental and control groups. Students' view on the problem-solving competency in physics with flipped learning using instructional design revealed that using instructional design for flipped classroom helps them identify and mobilize learned knowledge to solve problems because they have more time in class to integrate what they have learned.</i></p>

Introduction

The main goal of education is to develop students' problem-solving competencies. Problem-solving competencies require that students have a variety of competencies components, such as the ability to analyze problem situations, identify learned knowledge to find an appropriate solution, plan the solution, implement the solution, and evaluate the solution. Problem-solving competencies require that students learn by doing, they should change their learning experience. In our opinion, in traditional pedagogy, class time is devoted to building concepts, and students no longer have time to practice and develop problem-solving competencies. Therefore, students' problem-solving ability is not promoted effectively. There have been many studies on developing students' problem-solving abilities, but there has been little study on improving engineering students' problem-solving competencies in college physics courses. Thus, it is necessary to find a competency-based teaching model for engineering students. In the field of education, the flipped classroom is an instructional approach in which students are encouraged to learn concepts prior to class, class time is reserved for practicing problem-solving through collaborative work between teachers and students in class, and in post-class activities, students are provided with a complex problem to practice their ability to solve problems independently. Implementing a competency-based instructional model with Flipped Classroom requires teachers to design courses carefully, rationally, and effectively. To this end, we use the ADDIE model (Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate). This instructional design model is commonly used in science education to analyze, design, develop, and implement a course (Branch, 2009). In addition to improving the effectiveness of learning outcomes, the course is typically designed backward (McTighe & Thomas, 2003). We hypothesize that combining the ADDIE model and the backward design course to implement a competency-based instructional model with flipped classroom will improve engineering students' problem-solving competencies.

Literature Review

Competency-Based Teaching

In the field of education, competency-based problem-solving is defined as a student's ability to mobilize the learned knowledge and skills to solve problems related to the real-life world (Roegiers & Ketele, 2001). This teaching model is characterized by organizing content knowledge around the real problem using different types of assessment during the learning process with one rubric being an assessment tool for solving problem situations (Salazar-Torres et al., 2021). Once the instructional content and assessment strategy has been planned, the learning activities are carried out in which students are confronted with these problems and work in groups

toward a solution; they are the heart of the learning process. Competency-based teaching (CBT) emphasizes the application of prior knowledge to solve problems by developing students' skills. CBT is not about learning and memorizing content, but about identifying content that supports the development of students' competencies. Therefore, CBT must be analyzed, designed, developed, and implemented with an appropriate method.

Flipped classroom

In the Flipped Classroom (FC), students learn the main material for the course individually outside the classroom and then come to class to work through the content together. Following the work of Kong (2015), FC consists of three phases: before class, during class, and after class. In the pre-class activities, students are asked to watch the instructional videos and answer multiple-choice questions. During class time, students apply what they have learned at home to solve a problem together. In the after-class activities, students link the in-class and before-class activities to solve a complex problem. To improve students' problem-solving competencies in class, students are strictly required to learn the materials carefully at home. The FC model enhances student-directed learning (Rasheed et al., 2020). This model also promotes student initiative in learning.

Instructional design

In science education, Backward Design (BD) is usually used to design a lesson plan. The BD involves three phases, including setting the intended learning outcomes, planning the assessment strategy, and implementing the learning activities (McTighe & Thomas, 2003). In this study, the ADDIE model is used to "flip" instruction based on the BD. The model ADDIE consists of five phases including analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (Branch, 2009). In the stage of analysis, the teacher should analyze the learning needs of the students and the learning tasks that need to be completed to achieve the goals. During the analysis of the students' learning needs the teacher should analyze the students' profiles. In addition, the teacher should consider why the content knowledge is being taught using the FC model. Based on the intended learning outcomes and student profiles, the teacher establishes learning objectives that include core knowledge, skills, and developed competencies. In the stage of design, assessment strategies and learning activities are carefully planned. In the development phase, the assessment strategy and learning activities are adapted to create the training program. In the stage of implementation, learning activities are divided into three main phases: Contextualization, De-contextualization, and Re-contextualization. In the contextualization phase, students are placed in a situation where they are asked to solve a problem after they have acquired the concept, the law. De-contextualization is defined as a method in which students build core knowledge through student-teacher interaction, between student content, and between peers. Re-contextualization is the process of mobilizing and combining acquired knowledge in a new situation (Tardif, 1999). Thus, student achievement levels become evident during the re-contextualization phase. In the stage of evaluation, the teacher evaluates the student's level of performance against the intended learning goal.

The CBT model focuses on analyzing the learning situation, determining the problem, identifying the acquired knowledge to find a solution to the problem, planning a solution, implementing the solution, and evaluating the chosen solution, with the identification of acquired knowledge being at the heart of the competency approach. In our opinion, it is important to design the learning situation in such a way that students can mobilize their acquired knowledge in the learning process. From our teaching practice, we know that students have difficulty finding a solution to a problem if we only teach them content knowledge in class and then ask them to solve a situation, as shown by the results of the student surveys in the results session. Therefore, it is important to help students acquire knowledge before they go to class. In class, students practice problem-solving in collaboration with their teacher and classmates. In relation to this aspect, the FC model can be used to help students learn learning materials before going to class. Competency-based instruction using the FC model is structured as shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. Instructional design for Flipped Classroom

Competency Assessment

The competency-based approach leads to the assessment of student performance in complex situations in which students must use their acquired knowledge to solve a complex problem (De Ketele & Gerard, 2005). The assessment tool for competency-based learning is a rubric. There are several types of assessment in competency-based instruction, such as diagnostic assessment, formative assessment, and summative assessment. Diagnostic assessment is used to gather data about what students already know about the topic. Formative assessment helps the teacher monitor student progress during the learning process. Summative assessment is used to determine if students have met learning objectives.

Research Method

Research design

This study was conducted with first-year students in the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Cao Thang Technical College in Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam. A quasi-experimental design was used in this study, as students were not randomly assigned to conditions. Prior to the intervention study, a pretest was administered in both classes as a problem-solving test to determine the students' level of problem-solving skills. After the intervention study, a posttest was administered in both classes to determine the difference in problem-solving competencies between the experimental group and the control group. The independent variables are the teaching methods, while the dependent variable is the students' problem solving competencies.

Sample

The population of this study was all first-year students at the faculty of electrical and electronic engineering, Cao Thang Technical College, Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam. All first-year students at this faculty consist of seven classes. From the seven classes, two were selected and randomly assigned to an experimental group and a control group (experimental group, $N = 70$; control group, $N = 70$). This study was conducted in the second semester of the 2021-2022 academic year.

Instrument and data collection

- Quantitative data collection instrument

A problem-solving test is used as an instrument to gather the data. It was built based on the goal and learning outcome setting at Cao Thang Technical College related to energy and momentum, impulse and collision topics. A given problem solving test has been explored in the book entitled "Sears and Zemansky's University Physics with Modern Physics". The problem statement refers to the ballistic pendulum as follows: "A ballistic pendulum, a simple system for measuring the speed of a bullet. A bullet of mass $m_B = 5g$ makes a completely inelastic collision with a block of wood of mass $m_W = 2kg$ which is suspended like a pendulum. After the

impact, the block swings up to a maximum height $y = 3\text{cm}$. How to determine the initial speed of the bullet? (Young et al., 2013).

- Designing a rubric for competency assessment

Based on the definition of the students' competency in problem-solving in the literature section, a rubric for competency assessment is built to assess students' to determine problem, find out a solution, execute the solution, and evaluate the solution. The assessment tool is elaborated, as seen Table 1.

Table 1. Assessment instrument for students' problem-solving competency

Competencies	Performance	Items	Performance level		
			Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Determining problem (DP)	Extracting information	EI	Extracting incomplete information from the given problem	Extracting relatively complete information from the given problem	Extracting information from the given problem completely
	Identifying the physical quantity to be calculated	IPQ	Determining the speed of the bullet before collision is \vec{v}_1 , without the event diagram	Determining the speed of the bullet before collision is \vec{v}_1 , drawing the event diagram without stages of collision	Representing the speed of the bullet before collision is \vec{v}_1 , drawing the event diagram in two stages
Finding a solution (FS)	Analyzing the physical phenomena	APP	Analyzing this event in two stages generally	Analyzing this event in two stages, but clearly stating the embedding of the bullet in the block and (2) the pendulum swing of the bloc	Analyzing this event in two stages: (1) the embedding of the bullet in the block and (2) the pendulum swing of the bloc
	Solution planning	SP	Using only momentum conservation	Student don't select a coordinate system Using momentum conservation, and using energy conservation	Select a coordinate system Immediately after the collision, using momentum conservation in the first stage, and using energy conservation in the second stage
Executing	Mobilizing the learned knowledge	MLK	Writing only the law of momentums conservation or the law of energy conservation completely	Writing the law of momentums conservation and the law of energy conservation, but not complete	Writing the law of momentums conservation and the law of energy conservation completely
	Determining the relationship between known and unknown quantities	DRK-UNK	In the first stage:	In the first stage: $v_1 = \frac{m_B}{m_B + m_W} v_2$	In the first stage: $v_1 = \frac{m_B}{m_B + m_W} v_2$ In the second stage:

			$v_1 = \frac{m_B}{m_B + m_W} v_2$	In the second stage: $v_2 = \sqrt{2gh}$	$v_2 = \sqrt{2gh}$ Determining the speed of the bullet according to m_B , m_W , and h : $v_1 = \frac{m_B}{m_B + m_W} \sqrt{2gh}$
Validating the results	Finding the results	FR	Student cannot find the speed of the bullet	$v_1 = 307$ m/s	$v_1 = 307$ m/s, $v_2 = 0.767$ m/s
	Discussing the results	DR	Students do not mention their opinion	Students mention their opinion, but not complete	Student's opinion: The speeds v_1 and v_2 seem realistic.

- Validity and reliability of instrument

Instrument Validity

Content validation was used to check the given problem-solving for the pretest and posttest. It means that checking whether the problem-solving is met the physics learning outcomes. This problem-solving tool was examined by two physics teachers who teach the general physics for first-year engineering. From Williams' (2003) perspective, the validity of an instrument can be validated if it measures what we intend it to measure. Expert opinions of physics teachers help the researcher complete content validity.

Reliability of instrument

We use interrater reliability to determine the reliability of the instrument (Gisev et al., 2013). In this study, we use inter-rater reliability (IRR) using Cohen's Kappa to examine the consistency of decisions between two raters. The student tests are scored by two physics teachers. The data obtained were processed using SPSS software. To determine Cohen's Kappa, a pilot study was conducted with 70 students who were not included in the sample. After analyzing the data, Cohen's Kappa coefficients are presented as in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability of instrument using Cohen's kappa

Competencies	Items	Cohend' Value	Kappa	Approx. Sig.
Determining problem (DP)	EI	0.776		0.000
	IPQ	0.700		0.000
Finding a solution (FS)	APP	0.765		0.000
	SP	0.738		0.000
Executing	MLK	0.762		0.000
	DRK-UNK	0.741		0.000
Validating the results	FR	0.723		0.000
	DR	0.665		0.000

Table 2 shows that the kappa values range from 0.665 to 0.776 and that all p values are less than 0.05. Based on the work of Landis & Koch (1977), we found that the kappa values are considered substantial. These kappa values represent substantial strength of agreement. Thus, we conclude that the instrument is appropriate for the study.

- Qualitative data collection instrument

Qualitative research interviews are useful when a researcher seeks to understand the interviewee's opinion rather than to gain generalizable insights about large groups of people (McGrath et al., 2019). In this study, a semi-interview was conducted with students from the study sample before and after the intervention study. The author used the concept of saturation to collect the qualitative data, it means the point in time when the collection of new qualitative data no longer changes or changes little (Marshall et al., 2013). The content of the interview focuses on learning, teaching, and assessment related to the physics course in the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Cao Thang Technical College.

- Teaching organization

Designing, developing, and implementing

Based on the goal and learning outcome statements, the teacher identifies core knowledge related to work, energy and conservation of energy, momentum, and momentum theorem. The teacher also plans the assessment

strategy and learning activities for students. In addition, the teacher provides students with a learning scenario with the FC model.

The experimental class was delivered with FC while the control group was taught using the conventional method. In the control group, students are required to learn the content knowledge in class, and then do the homework at home, while students in the experimental group were taught using the FC with an instructional design model. The experimental class is divided into 7 groups, each group consist of 10 students. The learning scenario is depicted as seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Learning scenario with Flipped classroom

Stage	Topics	Goal and learning outcome	Learning content	Learning activities
Pre-class	Complex situation is introduced to students	Learning strategies and assessment of energy topics	Content knowledge list of energy topic	Drop hammer collides with a pile
	Work	Students' ability to calculate work done by a constant force	Work of force Power	Watching the instructional video, completing the multiple choice question
In-class		Developing students 'problem-solving competency	Determining work of several forces	Working in collaboration
Post-class		Extending knowledge	Apply work of force for news situations	Working independently
Pre-class	Kinetic energy and work-energy theorem	Students' ability to apply the work-energy theorem	Kinetic energy Work – energy theorem	Watching the instructional video, completing the multiple choice question
In Class		Developing students 'problem-solving competency	Determining forces on a hammerhead by using the work – energy theorem	Working in collaboration
Post-class		Extending knowledge	Applying the work energy with varying force	Working independently
Pre-class	Potential energy and energy conservation	Students' ability to apply the energy conservation	Potential energy Elastic potential energy Energy conservation	Watching the instructional video, completing the multiple choice question
In-class		Developing students 'problem-solving competency	Determining height of a baseball from energy conservation	Working in collaboration
Post-class		Extending knowledge	Applying energy conservation for motion with gravitational, elastic, and friction forces	Working independently
Pre-class	Momentum, impulse, and collision	Students' ability to apply the momentum conservation and energy conservation	Momentum, impulse-momentum theorem Types of collision	Watching the instructional video, completing the multiple choice question
In-class		Developing students 'problem-solving competency	Determining forces on a hammerhead by using the work – energy theorem	Working in collaboration
Post-class		Extending knowledge	Applying energy conservation for	Working independently

			motion with gravitational, elastic, and friction forces	
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- Data collection

Quantitative data collection

Before the intervention study, both the experimental and control group participated in the pretest. After the pretest was over, the experimental group studied the learning topics using the FC model, as seen in Table 3. For the control group, the same content knowledge was delivered using the conventional method. Both the experimental and control groups were taught in parallel for 15 teaching hours. The posttest was applied to both groups. The problem-solving test related to “ballistic pendulum”, as seen in “instrument and data collection” session, was applied for the experimental and control groups. Both groups took the pretest and posttest during 45 minutes. After collecting the tests, we used the rubric for competency assessment, as seen in Table 1, to evaluate the students’ performance level. The score obtained from grading the students’ performance level was considered quantitative data collection.

Qualitative data collection

Semi-interviews were used to collect data before and after the intervention study. Since the experimental group is divided into 7 groups, one student was randomly selected from each group, and the number of selected students was designated as S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, and S7. The content of the interviews before and after the experiment was the same and related to topics such as learning style, ability to apply knowledge in practice, problem-solving ability, and the importance of studying physics for engineering students.

- Data processing

Quantitative data processing

The software SPSS 22 was used in this study as a tool for analysis. The data were collected before and after applying of FC using an instructional design model. After coding the quantitative data using SPSS 22, the Mann-Whitney U test is used because the data were not normally distributed. To identify if there exists significant differences in the physics competencies between the experimental group and the control group, we test a null hypothesis (H0) and an alternative hypothesis (H1) as follows:

H0: There are no significant differences in physics competencies between the experimental group and the control group.

H1: There are significant differences in physics competencies between the experimental group and the control group.

Qualitative data processing

The thematic analysis is used in this study because this analysis method is an appropriate to use when seeking to understand a set of experiences, viewpoint, across a data set (Braun & Clarke, 2012). In this study, the thematic analysis is used based on the work of (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Data processing were conducted in the following steps: Step 1, the author transcribed the audio data and familiar with them by reading several times. Step 2, the author conducted a coding process. The third step involves examination of codes and categorize them into themes. Step 4, the author reviewed the themes. Step 5, the author defined and named the themes. The final step involved writing up the analysis results.

Results

Quantitative results session

To test whether there were differences in academic performance between the experimental and control groups, independent-samples t tests were performed for the pretest and posttest. The data obtained from the pretest and posttest were statistically analysed. The results of the statistical calculations are presented below.

Table 4. Pretest mean score of the control group and experimental group

Competencies	Items	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Z	Sig. (2-tailed)
Determining problem (DP)	EI	Experimental	70	72.50	5075.00	2310.000	-0.674	0.500
		Control	70	68.50	4795.00			
Finding solution (FS)	IPQ	Experimental	70	71.47	5003.00	2382.000	-0.366	0.714
		Control	70	69.53	4867.00			
Executing	APP	Experimental	70	69.21	4844.50	2359.500	-0.443	0.658
		Control	70	71.79	5025.50			
Executing	SP	Experimental	70	74.29	5200.00	2185.000	-1.548	0.122
		Control	70	66.71	4670.00			
Executing	MLK	Experimental	70	71.50	5005.00	2380.000	-0.352	0.725
		Control	70	69.50	4865.00			

Validating the results	DR	Experimental	70	72.63	5084.00	2301.000	-0.742	0.458
	K-UN	Control	70	68.37	4786.00			
	K							
	FR	Experimental	70	72.95	5106.00	2278.500	-0.809	0.418
		Control	70	68.05	4763.50			
	DR	Experimental	70	68.91	4824.00	2339.000	-0.515	0.607
		Control	70	72.09	5046.00			

The Table 4 shows that the mean rank is higher in the experimental group than in the control group, except for APP and DR. To determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the two groups, we need to examine the statistical test. All p-values are greater than 0.05 at 95% confidence interval (95%CI), with Mann Whitney U and Z values listed in Table 4. Therefore, we can accept the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the achievement level in physics between the experimental and control groups. This means that before the intervention study, both the experimental and control groups had the same achievement level in physics.

Table 5. Posttest mean score of the control group and experimental group

Competencies	Items	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Z	Sig. (2-tailed)
Determining problem (DP)	EI	Experimental	70	79.00	5530.00	1855.000	-2.931	0.003
		Control	70	62.00	4340.00			
Finding solution (FS)	IPQ	Experimental	70	77.81	5447.00	1938.000	-2.744	0.006
		Control	70	63.19	4423.00			
Validating the results	APP	Experimental	70	76.00	5320.00	2065.000	-2.705	0.007
		Control	70	65.00	4550.00			
Executing	SP	Experimental	70	77.59	5431.00	1954.000	-2.484	0.013
		Control	70	63.41	4439.00			
Validating the results	MLK	Experimental	70	81.50	5705.00	1680.000	-4.239	0.000
		Control	70	59.50	4165.00			
Validating the results	DRK-UNK	Experimental	70	78.00	5460.00	1925.000	-2.818	0.005
		Control	70	63.00	4410.00			
Validating the results	FR	Experimental	70	78.76	5513.50	1871.500	-2.887	0.004
		Control	70	62.24	4356.50			
Validating the results	DR	Experimental	70	77.77	5444.00	1941.000	-2.540	0.011
		Control	70	63.23	4426.00			

The results show that the experimental group had a mean rank between 81.50 and 77.59, while the control group had a mean rank between 59.50 and 65.00. Overall, the mean ranks in the experimental group are higher than those in the control group. Furthermore, all p-values are less than 0.05 (95%CI), with Mann Whitney U and Z values, shown in Table 5. Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis that there is no difference in physics performance between the experimental and control groups. This means that after the intervention study with the flipped classroom using an instructional design, the achievement level in physics was improved.

Qualitative results session

RQ: Students 'opinion about learning activities toward the physics course?

Before intervention study

Seven students were randomly selected from the study sample, including experimental and control class. These students 'opinion about learning physics activities are described in Table 6.

Table 6. Students' opinion about the physics course before intervention study

Theme	Code	Advantage		Disadvantages	
		Number of students	students 'opinion	Number of students	Students'opinion
Learning activities	Situated learning	0		7	These students mentioned that learning lessons separate from real world
	Building knowledge	S3, S5	These students mentioned that they did not spend much	S1,S2,S4, S6,S7	These students mentioned that they passively receive new

			time in building knowledge		knowledge
	Applying knowledge	0	0	7	All students stated that they could not integrate the learned knowledge into the real world
	Problem-solving method	0	0	7	All students indicated that they hadn't had the opportunity to practice problem solving skills
	Collaborative work	0	0	7	All students indicated that they didn't have the opportunity to collaborate
Assessment	Assessment tools	S3, S7	These students stated that this assessment tool ensures objectivity in the assessment process	S1,S2, S4, S5, S6	In their view, assessment focused on multiple-choice questions didn't help them improve their problem-solving skills
	Stage of assessment	0	0	7	The assessment is only used when the course is over.
	Feedback	0	0	7	Students rarely receive feedback from teachers.
	Students' progress	0	0	7	Students are unable to identify current performance in relation to the learning objective
	Lecture	S3	This student mentioned that the well-structured course helps students follow easy the learning process	S1,S2, S4, S5, S6, S7	These students mentioned that they are demotivated while learning
Teaching organizations	Collaborative learning	0	0	7	All students indicated that they didn't have the opportunity to collaborate
	Learning material	0	0	7	All students indicated that they didn't have the opportunity to explore various resources and learning materials
	Integrated teaching	0	0	7	All students stated that they hadn't had the opportunity to integrate the knowledge they'd learned into the real world

Table 6 shows that all students indicated that situated learning excluded the real world, that they passively absorbed new knowledge, that they did not have the opportunity to receive feedback from the teacher, and that they could not integrate the knowledge they learned into the real world. As a result, they did not have the opportunity to practice problem-solving competencies.

After intervention study

Seven students were randomly selected from the experimental group. These students' opinion about learning physics activities are described in Table VII.

Table 7. Students' opinion about the physics course after intervention study

Theme	Code	Advantage		Disadvantages	
		Number of students	students' opinion	Number of students	Students' opinion
Learning activities	Situated learning	7	These students mentioned that learning lessons were placed in the real world	0	
	Building knowledge	S1,S3,S4 S5,S6	These students mentioned that they can build new knowledge through the instructional videos	S2,S7	These students mentioned that they spend too much time watching videos
	Applying knowledge	S1, S3,S4 S5,S6	These students mentioned that they can link the learned knowledge to real world as they have more time in-class to integrate the learned knowledge	S2, S7	These students mentioned that they lack time for practicing exercises
	Problem-solving method	7	All these students stated that they had the opportunity to practice problem-solving skills	0	
	Collaborative work	7	These students indicated that they had the opportunity to collaborate	0	
	Assessment tools	S1,S2, S4, S5, S6, S7	The various assessment tools help students identify strengths and weaknesses	S3	This student mentioned the rubric assessment is sometimes inaccurate
	Stage of assessment	S1,S2, S4, S5, S6, S7	The diagnostic assessment helps them determine the current performance level to plan the learning strategy.	S3	This student mentioned that the assessment takes too much study time
Assessment	Feedback	S1,S2, S3,S4, S5, S6	All students indicated that teacher feedback helps them regulate their current performance in terms of learning outcomes	S7	This student mentioned that sometimes formative assessment is not done in a timely manner

	Students' progress	7	All students can identify the current level of performance in relation to the learning objective	0	0
Teaching organizations	Diagnostic Assessment	7	Students indicated that diagnostic assessment is important to determine the initial level of knowledge related to news instruction. This helps them plan learning strategies	0	0
	Scenario teaching	7	All students indicated that scenario teaching helps them create their learning plan during the learning process	0	0
	Learning with the Flipped classroom	S1,S2, S3,S4, S5, S6	These students said that pre-class activities help them practice problem solving effectively in class	S7	This student stated that the activities before class take up too much time
	Integrated teaching	7	All students indicated that they had the opportunity to integrate the learned knowledge into the real world	0	0

Table 7 shows that all students indicated that the learning activities took place in a context that related to a real-world problem. They built new knowledge based on their prior knowledge and skills. They were able to integrate the learned knowledge into a complex situation to solve the problem, and they had the opportunity to practice problem-solving in class. As a result, students' problem-solving competencies were improved.

Discussion

The results show that there is a statistically significant difference in academic achievement between the experimental and control groups, which means that Flipped Classroom with the ADDIE model improved the development of students' problem-solving competencies, as shown in Table 5. This explains that the analysis and design of a competency-based course play an important role in the development of students' problem-solving competencies. In the analysis phase, the teacher needs to analyze the learning needs of the students. On the other hand, the teacher must analyze learning outcomes, content knowledge, and assessment strategy. In order to help students achieve the intended learning outcomes, the teacher must develop an instructional strategy. In this study, according to the model FC, the teaching strategy consists of three phases: Contextualization, De-contextualization, and Re-contextualization. The purpose of the contextualization phase is to familiarize students with the problem-solving situation, but on the other hand, this phase also guides students in exploring the content knowledge in the de-contextualization phase. Contextualization helps students understand the constructed meaningful knowledge. In addition, contextualization also prepares students for problem-solving in the re-contextualization phase. Thus, with FC, students have more time in class to practice how to integrate the acquired knowledge into a situation. In this study, we put students in the situation "drop hammer collides with a pile" at the beginning of the topic of energy. By analyzing this situation, students had to learn the main contents such as kinetic energy and work-energy theorem, potential energy and conservation of

energy, momentum, impulse, and collisions. In the implementation of the FC model, students have more time in class, the teacher supports students in integrating the acquired knowledge to solve problems, which has improved students' competencies. Also, because students receive real-time feedback from teachers, they can overcome difficulties when faced with a problem-solving situation.

In order to optimize the effectiveness of integrating content knowledge to solve the problem, on the one hand, the teacher requires students to watch the video lecture, answer the quizzes, and complete the assignments; on the other hand, the teacher has provided students with a rubric for competency assessment before class. Therefore, the elaboration of the learning scenario is important for students to clearly understand what they are learning in the stages of FC. From the interview after the intervention study, the students mentioned that they spend much time watching videos before class. Therefore, they were negatively affected by the FC model. In our viewpoint, it is necessary to create short videos and to give students the necessary instructions to help them grasp declarative knowledge more easily while watching those videos. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that this problem is eliminated by creating short videos with the necessary instructions to help students complete the assigned task before class (Çelik, 2021).

In our opinion, the selection of content to be used for the FC is also important. In this study, the topic of energy, as shown in Table III, was also covered in the 10th grade physics program in high school, Vietnam. Consequently, the use of the FC model for this topic is appropriate for first-year electrical and electronic engineering students. This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that not all types of content knowledge are suitable for the FC method (Chen, 2021).

Based on our findings, we also recommend that an instructional design for the FC model should be based on contextual learning in relation to a real-world problem, that new knowledge should be built on the basics of the prior knowledge, and that new knowledge should be applied to a complex situation to promote students' problem-solving competencies.

Conclusion

In this study, the FC model was used in a physics course for first-year undergraduate students in the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Cao Thang Technical College. The results show that there is a difference in academic performance between the experimental and control groups. The experimental group in which FC was used achieved better results than the control group which used the conventional method. The results show that the FC model improves student learning and helps them identify, combine, and integrate learned knowledge to solve a complex problem. This research has implications for designing a course using the FC model to promote students' problem-solving competencies in physics.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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